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The challenges of implementing the fair value accounting as per IFRS 9 (2013) – An empirical study on the listed corporations in Saudi Arabia Stock Exchange Market

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Abstract

The purpose of the current study was to examine the role and relevance of International Financial Reporting Standards and fair value accounting measurements. Adoption and implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards has been established to be the key in ensuring improved reliability as well as compatibility of corporate reports. In addition, Fair Value Accounting is used in the recording of liability assumed and assets acquired by a business corporation. Descriptive survey research design was used where quantitative approach was employed in the study. Research participants were CFOs and financial advisors working in Saudi Arabian financial industry. The sample size was 65 and opinions as well as views of the respondents were gathered using closed ended questionnaires. Majority of the respondents were aged over 25 years with majority of the research participants having at least bachelor's degree. It was found out that IFRS 9 (2013) is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices with majority of the respondents agreeing that IFRS 9 (2013) is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market. IFRS 9 (2013) is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard. Most of the research participants agreed that Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia.

Keywords: Fair Value Accounting, IFRS 9 (2013), International Financial Reporting Standards, Internal Management Reporting Practices, Saudi Arabia Stock Exchange Market

1. Introduction

Tremendous changes have been observed in various industries globally with respect to changes in doing business. According to Jain (2011) financial reporting process, which presents business activities of entities, has also realized remarkable change. The commencement of such change can be traced to 2005 when European Union made it compulsory for all publicly traded companies to be able to present consolidated financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) starting January 2005 (Mukherjee, 2010). Prior to instruction of International Financial Reporting Standards in 2005, companies in Asian and European countries were allowed to use International Accounting Standards. Presently several countries with developed capital market have embraced and adopted International

Financial Reporting Standards while others are in the process of adopting International Financial Reporting Standards specifically for reporting purposes (Chen, Tang, Jiang, and Lin, 2010). In the process of adopting International Financial Reporting Standards, countries tend to replace their national standards with International Financial Reporting Standards. On the other hand, Paglietti (2009) found out that some countries have adopted the International Financial Reporting Standards by first reviewing the IFRS to ensure that its suitability with the prevailing social, economic and political conditions in their countries thereby making them adopt the IFRS verbatim or adopt the IFRSs with minor changes (Iatridis, 2010). In the contemporary world, international accounting standard board and financial accounting standard board are shifting from historic cost accounting to fair value accounting with respect to making accounting standards (Goncharov, 2009). Kohlbeck (2008) observed that fair value as a measurement basis in accounting - has become quite significant and is increasingly being adopted due to its importance in making accounting standards, which is the key to improving financial reporting.

The main aim of the study is to examine the role and relevance of International Financial Reporting Standards and fair value accounting measurements. In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the following research objectives were designed accordingly:

1. To study the impact of IFRS 9 adoption on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices.
2. To understand how financial asset of listed companies may be measured as per FVA under IFRS 9.
3. To recognize the profit/losses that are expected to occur over the life of the asset and for the organization.

The study is divided into five main sections namely introduction as section one; section two is literature review; section three is research methodology; section four is results and interpretation and section five is conclusion. Section I presents the background and objectives of the study. Section II presents a brief review of past studies on International Financial Reporting Standards and fair value accounting. Section III presents the research methodology used in the study, model of the study and hypotheses tested in the study. Section IV presents the results and interpretation, i.e. statistical analysis of responses, interpretation of the findings and discussion of the research findings. Section V presents the Conclusion, which summaries the whole study of the implications of adopting IFRS 9 (2013) on the listed corporations in Saudi Arabia Stock Exchange Market.

The study suffered from a few limitations such as time, financial and geographical limitation. The study was to be completed within a given period of time, which made it necessary to reduce the focus of the study. Also, financial constraints could not allow extensive research. Primary data used in the paper were gathered mainly from CFOs and financial advisors from Saudi Arabia, thereby limiting the study geographically.

2. Literature Review

There has been great interest over the past three decades among professional, accountancy organizations, standard-setters, regulators, academia and policymakers as well as among other stakeholders with regards to improving reliability and compatibility of corporate reports as noted by Qu, Fong, and Oliver, (2012). Adoption and implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards has been established to be the key in ensuring improved reliability as well as compatibility of corporate reports (Jones, 2010; Epstein, 2009; Lantto. and Sahlströ, 2009). International Financial Reporting Standards is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard, which is issued by International accounting Standards Board (Devalle, Onali and Magarini, 2010). The standards used are popularly recognized to play a significant role in producing more accurate, detailed and timely financial accounting information, which is key to informed evaluation in equity markets thereby lowering risk appropriately for investors. Adoption and implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards among companies according to Armstrong, Barth, Jagolinzer, and Riedl, (2010) plays a significant role in promoting consistency in reporting format in companies across nations, which in turn reduces the cost to investors especially with respect to financial information processing. Such development has been found to be important in the business environment because it leads to improved capital market efficiency.

International Financial Reporting Standards according to Dritsas and Petrakos (2014) helps in financial information processing which affects the entities and business environment as well. For instance, companies that have sound and internationally comparable corporate financial reporting, which meets both the expectations and needs of financial markets is important because it helps in improving the confidence of investors apart from facilitating risk assessment in making investment decision and helping in reducing cost of capital (Clements, Neill, and Stovall, 2010). In addition, following the globalization, which eliminated both national and regional boundaries, International Financial Reporting Standards helps in the elimination of international differences in the global financial reporting, which encourage mobilization and efficient allocation of financial resources especially investment resources, which is needed for economic development (Bhattacharjee and Islam, 2009; Chand and White, 2007). Convergence of the International Financial Reporting Standards in European countries as well as in Australia has made it necessary for scholars to investigate whether such convergence can lead to improvement of quality of financial information consistently across various countries. Before the IFRS came into force in 2005, majority of the European organizations used domestic accounting standards (Steffee, 2009). The application of the IFRS according to Callao, Jarne, and Laínez (2007) brought into being one of the massive financial reporting shift events, which occurred in the recent years among the European countries. Based on Armstrong *et al.* (2008) the realization of full adoption of IFRS as designed by the IASB resulted in a harmonized set of financial reporting standards not just for the European countries but also for those engaging with them. Zhou, Xiong, Y. and Ganguli (2009) noted that high among the interesting subjects on debate about the IFRS are about its benefits as well as costs during implementation, the worldwide financial reporting harmonization impacts in case of its readjustments due to the adoption process. Study on the impact of adopting International Financial Reporting Standards on listed companies according to Terzi, Oktem and Sen (2013) indicate existence of significant differences in the number of accounts in the financial statements, which include net assets, long-term liability, fixed assets and inventories. The study was based on examination of specific frequently used

financial ratios related to financial statements of companies listed in the stock exchange market (Barth, Wayne, Mark, 2008).

Many entities are shifting from the historic cost accounting to fair value accounting due to the advantage associated with the fair value accounting in making accounting standards (Paananen, and Lin, 2009). Several studies have been conducted on the value-relevance as well as reliability of fair value disclosures of financial information (Li and Kyu, 2010). Fair value accounting is being used increasingly in financial reporting. The use of fair value in financial reporting has been ascertained to range from measuring majority of financial instruments at fair value in order to impairments calculation as well as the recording of liability assumed and assets acquired in a business combination (Li, 2010; Iatridis and Rouvolis, 2010; Cai, and Wong, 2010). Setters of accounting standard continue to employ fair value accounting as a relevant measure of both liabilities and assets for the purposes of financial reporting (Zhu, 2008). IASB and FASB have provided necessary guidance on the use of fair value in order to ensure consistency associated with fair value measurements. The issued guidance offers a framework for measuring liabilities and assets at fair value and requiring at the same time robust disclosures around judgments as well as inputs behind the measurements. Use of fair value account has a number of impacts on companies. For instance, increased use of fair value demands that entities refresh their measurements procedures and policies (Peng, 2008). Suitably and robust disclosures in financial statements are significant in providing investors with important financial information which is key to their decision making since they inform investors of methods of measurements as well as uncertainty (Deng, 2005). It is necessary therefore, that entities analyze how fair value is determined when they exist on active market and ascertain procedure needed to develop the appropriate disclosure (Haw, Park, Qi, and Wu, 2003). For companies, the primary objective of fair value measurement is to estimate appropriately the prices at which the positions they currently hold would change hands in orderly transactions based on current conditions and information (Isabel, 2007). In order to achieve this, it is important that companies incorporate fully current information about future cash flows and current risk-adjusted discount rates into their fair value measurements.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research hypotheses

There is increased use of International Financial Reporting Standards and fair value accounting among companies due to the role that they play in financial information provision. The following hypotheses were designed in accordance with research objectives.

H1: There is positive impact of IFRS 9 (2013) adoption on the stock market of Saudi Arabia.

Since the introduction of International Financial Reporting Standards in 2005 in Europe, it has been used on increased basis across different countries to provide financial information, which is the key in informed decision-making. Investigating the impact of IFRS 9 (2013) adoption on the stock market of Saudi Arabia is significant in the sense that it highlights how IFRS impact companies.

H2: There is a significant relationship between IFRS 9 (2013) adoption and internal management reporting practices.

Investigation on whether implementation of fair value accounting is important for financial reporting of internal management reporting practices with respect to maintaining transparency is crucial in meeting the objectives of the study. A number of advantages of fair value accounting in making accounting standards have been highlighted in past studies; hence, the investigation of importance of fair value accounting in ensuring transparency with respect to internal management reporting practices is a significant concern in the study.

H3: Fair value accounting is a very important measurement tool for financial assets of listed companies in Saudi Arabia.

The role of fair value accounting, across various industries in Saudi Arabia is important to consumers of the study. Hence examining fair value accounting as a measurement tool for financial asset of listed entities in Saudi Arabia is an important area for research in the study.

H4: Fair value accounting when implemented as per IFRS 9 (2013) enables appropriate recognition of profit/losses of an asset.

The study also investigated the impact of implementation of fair values accounting in accordance with IFRS and how such implementation relate to recognition of losses and profit of asset in companies in Saudi Arabia.

3.2 Model of the Study

The research used both primary and secondary data. Secondary data was derived from past studies on fair value accounting and IFRS. Primary data on the other hand, was derived from chief financial officers and financial advisors in Saudi Arabia. Quantitative model, which is also known as positivist was employed in the study to achieve the purpose of the study. The choice of the model was informed by the fact that it is the most appropriate to test hypothesis as well as to analyze various attributes of variables using statistical methods in order to provide answers to complex research questions. Closed ended questionnaires designed in accordance to 5-likert scale were used in the study to collect data from chief financial officers and financial advisors in Saudi Arabia. A total of 65 respondents were targeted in the study. Purposive sampling method

was used to identify respondent who participated in the study. The collected data were then extracted and analyzed using chi-square test and descriptive statistical analysis. Research ethics was upheld during the entire research process.

4. Results and Interpretation

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1 and Figure 1 show that 7.7% of the respondents who participated in the study were aged 18-24 years, 20% were aged 25-34 years, 44.6% were aged 35-44 years and 15.4% were aged 45-60 years while 12.3% were aged over 60 years.

Table 1: Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-24 years	5	7.7	7.7	7.7
25-34 years	13	20.0	20.0	27.7
35-44 years	29	44.6	44.6	72.3
45-60 years	10	15.4	15.4	87.7
60+ years	8	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1: Age

Table 2 and Figure 2 indicate that 1.5% of the respondents who participated in the study had O/A level of education, 9.2% had diploma, 69.2% had bachelor's degree, 15.4% had master's degree and 4.6% had doctorate degree.

Table 2: Education Level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
O/A - Level	1	1.5	1.5	1.5
Diploma	6	9.2	9.2	10.8
Bachelor's degree	45	69.2	69.2	80.0
Master's degree	10	15.4	15.4	95.4
Doctorate's degree	3	4.6	4.6	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Education Level

As indicated in the Figure 3 and Table 3, 61.5% of the respondents who participated in the study were male while 38.5% were female.

Table 3: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	40	61.5	61.5	61.5
Valid Female	25	38.5	38.5	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Gender

Table 4 and Figure 4 show that 50.8% of the respondents who participated in the study were CFOs while 49.2% were financial advisors.

Table 4: Designation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
CFO	33	50.8	50.8	50.8
Valid Financial Advisor	32	49.2	49.2	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4: Designation

As shown in Table 5 and Figure 5 4.6% of the respondents who participated in the study had worked in the finance industry for less than 1 year, 7.7% had worked for 1-5 years, 35.4% had worked for 6-10 years and 52.3% of had worked in the industry for more than 10 years.

Table 5: Experience

For how long time have you been working in the industry?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1 year	3	4.6	4.6	4.6
1-5 years	5	7.7	7.7	12.3
Valid 6-10 years	23	35.4	35.4	47.7
More than 10 years	34	52.3	52.3	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

For how long time have you been working in the industry?

Figure 5: Experience

Table 6 and Figure 6 indicate that up to 98.5% of all the respondents who participated in the study were well conversant with the subject of IFRS 9 while 1.5% were not conversant with the subject.

Table 6: Conversance

Are you well conversant with the subject of IFRS 9?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	64	98.5	98.5	98.5
Valid No	1	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6: Conversance

Chi-square Test

H1: There is positive impact of IFRS 9 adoption on the stock market of Saudi Arabia

In order to test whether there is relationship between “IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market” and “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”; chi-square was used to test for equal proportion of the variables.

Table 7: Crosstabulation Test 1

IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market *
IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices

			IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	
IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	0	0	0	1	1
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	1.5%
	Disagree	Count	1	1	0	0	1	3
		% of Total	1.5%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	4.6%
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Count	0	0	2	0	6	8
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	3.1%	0.0%	9.2%	12.3%
	Agree	Count	1	2	1	14	12	30
		% of Total	1.5%	3.1%	1.5%	21.5%	18.5%	46.2%
	Strongly Agree	Count	1	1	2	3	16	23
		% of Total	1.5%	1.5%	3.1%	4.6%	24.6%	35.4%
	Total	Count	3	4	5	17	36	65
		% of Total	4.6%	6.2%	7.7%	26.2%	55.4%	100.0%

Table 8 shows p value to be 0.040. Since the p value is less than α , which is 0.05, it implies that there is significant relationship between “IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market” and “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”. The row percentages in Table 7 shows that majority of the respondents comprising of over 81% who agreed that “IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market” also agreed that “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”.

Table 8: Chi-Square Tests 1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.143 ^a	16	.040
Likelihood Ratio	25.049	16	.069
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.165	1	.280
N of Valid Cases	65		

a. 21 cells (84.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

H2: There is a significant relationship between IFRS 9 adoption and internal management reporting practices

In order to test whether there is relationship between “IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard” and “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”; chi-square was used to test for equal proportion of the variables.

Table 9: Crosstabulation Test 2

IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard * IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices Crosstabulation

			IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	
IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	0	0	2	2	4
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.1%	3.1%	6.2%
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%
	Agree	Count	1	1	3	0	15	20
		% of Total	1.5%	1.5%	4.6%	0.0%	23.1%	30.8%
	Strongly Agree	Count	2	4	1	18	15	40
		% of Total	3.1%	6.2%	1.5%	27.7%	23.1%	61.5%
Total	Count	3	5	5	20	32	65	
	% of Total	4.6%	7.7%	7.7%	30.8%	49.2%	100.0%	

Table 10 shows p value to be 0.004. Since the p value is less than α , which is 0.05, it implies that there is significant relationship between “IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard” and “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”. The row percentages in Table 9 shows that majority of the respondents comprising of over 80% who agreed that “IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard” also agreed that “IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices”.

Table 10: Chi-Square Tests 2**Chi-Square Tests**

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.159 ^a	12	.004
Likelihood Ratio	28.760	12	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	.812	1	.368
N of Valid Cases	65		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

H3: Fair value accounting is a very important measurement tool for financial assets of listed companies in Saudi Arabia

In order to test whether there is relationship between “Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia” and “Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia”; chi-square was used to test for equal proportion of the variables.

Table 11: Crosstabulation Test 3

Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia * Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia Crosstabulation

			Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	0	0	1	0	1
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	1.5%
	Disagree	Count	1	0	0	0	2	3
		% of Total	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.1%	4.6%
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Count	0	1	0	4	1	6
		% of Total	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	6.2%	1.5%	9.2%
	Agree	Count	3	4	2	3	22	34
		% of Total	4.6%	6.2%	3.1%	4.6%	33.8%	52.3%
	Strongly Agree	Count	0	0	0	1	20	21
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	30.8%	32.3%
	Total	Count	4	5	2	9	45	65
		% of Total	6.2%	7.7%	3.1%	13.8%	69.2%	100.0%

Table 12 shows p value to be 0.003. Since the p value is less than α , which is 0.05, it implies that there is significant relationship between “Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia” and “Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia”. The row percentages in Table 11 shows that majority of the respondents comprising of over 83% who agreed that “Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia” also agreed that “Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia”.

Table 12: Chi-Square Tests 3**Chi-Square Tests**

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35.805 ^a	16	.003
Likelihood Ratio	31.553	16	.011
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.219	1	.013
N of Valid Cases	65		

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

H4: Fair value accounting when implemented as per IFRS 9 enables appropriate recognition of profit/losses of an asset

In order to test whether there is relationship between “The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia” and “When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9, it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset”; chi-square was used to test for equal proportion of the variables.

Table 13: Crosstabulation Test 4

The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia * When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9, it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset Crosstabulation

			When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9, it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	
The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	1	0	0	0	1
		% of Total	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%
	Disagree	Count	0	1	0	2	1	4
		% of Total	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	3.1%	1.5%	6.2%
	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Count	0	1	1	1	4	7
		% of Total	0.0%	1.5%	1.5%	1.5%	6.2%	10.8%
	Agree	Count	0	0	0	11	6	17
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	16.9%	9.2%	26.2%
	Strongly Agree	Count	1	4	1	6	24	36
		% of Total	1.5%	6.2%	1.5%	9.2%	36.9%	55.4%
	Total	Count	1	7	2	20	35	65
		% of Total	1.5%	10.8%	3.1%	30.8%	53.8%	100.0%

Table 14 shows p value to be 0.033. Since the p value is less than α , which is 0.05, it implies that there is significant relationship between “The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia” and “When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9, it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset”. The row percentages in Table 13 show that majority of the respondents comprising of over 81% who agreed that “The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia” also agreed that “When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9; it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset”.

Table 14: Chi-Square Tests 1

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.865 ^a	16	.033
Likelihood Ratio	24.531	16	.079
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.077	1	.079
N of Valid Cases	65		

a. 21 cells (84.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

5. Conclusion

The study on the role and relevance of International Financial Reporting Standards and fair value accounting measurements was designed to investigate the impact of IFRS 9 (2013) adoption on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices and to understand how financial asset of listed companies may be measured as per FVA under IFRS 9 (2013). Descriptive survey research design was used where quantitative approach was employed in the study. Research participants were CFOs and financial advisors working in Saudi Arabian financial industry. The sample size was 65 and opinions as well as views of the respondents were gathered using closed ended questionnaires. Majority of the respondents were aged 25 years and above 89% of the respondents having at least bachelor's degree. Most of the respondents were male and more than 87% having acquired at least 6 years experience working in the industry.

The current study established that IFRS 9 (2013) is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices with majority of the respondents agreeing that IFRS 9 (2013) is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market. IFRS 9 (2013) was also found to play important role in improving financial reporting among corporations in Saudi Arabia. Besides, IFRS 9 (2013) is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard. Fair Value Accounting was found to have led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia. Majority of the respondents agreed that both FVA and IFRS 9 (2013) are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia. The study also ascertained that when FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9 (2013), it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset. It was found out that the stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia.

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APPENDICES

Appendix One: Survey Questionnaire

Dear Respondent,

This is an academic survey on “the challenges of implementing the fair value accounting as per IFRS 9 (2013) – an empirical study on the listed corporations in Saudi Arabia Stock Exchange Market”. The survey requires your **HONEST** response with regard to every section of the questionnaire. Since this is an academic survey, your views in the survey will be held private and used only for purposes of achieving the research objectives. Your personal details will remain anonymous to any third party.

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHIC AND GENERAL WORK INFORMATION

General Information (Please Select the Appropriate Choice by Marking One Check-Box)
1. Age: <input type="checkbox"/> 18- 24 years <input type="checkbox"/> 25-34 years <input type="checkbox"/> 35-44 years <input type="checkbox"/> 45-60 years <input type="checkbox"/> 60+ years
2. Education Level: <input type="checkbox"/> O/A-Level <input type="checkbox"/> Diploma <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor’s degree <input type="checkbox"/> Master’s degree <input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate’s degree
3. Gender: <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female
4. Designation: <input type="checkbox"/> CFO <input type="checkbox"/> Financial advisor
5. For how long time have you been working in the industry? <input type="checkbox"/> Less than 1 year <input type="checkbox"/> 1 - 5 years <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> More than 10 years

SECTION 2: WORK EXPERIENCE AND CONVERSANCE

6. Are you well conversant with the subject of IFRS 9?

Yes No

SECTION 3: SHOW YOUR LEVEL OF AGREEMENT/DISAGREEMENT

Please mark with a tick only one answer which shows your level of view based on your experience with the below listed statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
7. IFRS 9 is used on the stock market of Saudi Arabia and on internal management reporting practices	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
8. IFRS 9 is used to measure financial asset of listed companies in Saudi Arabian stock exchange market	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
9. IFRS 9 has played important role in improving financial reporting among corporations in Saudi Arabia	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
10. IFRS 9 is considered as a set of principles-based and high quality financial reporting standard	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
11. Fair Value Accounting has led to reliability of financial information of companies in Saudi Arabia	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
12. Fair Value Accounting is used in the recording of liability assumed and assets acquired by a business corporation	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
13. Fair value accounting has contributed to emergence of suitably and robust disclosures in financial statements leading to investors' confidence	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

14. Both FVA and IFRS 9 are used to measure financial assets of listed corporations in Saudi Arabia	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
15. Implementation of FVA as per IFRS 9 is very important for financial reporting of internal management reporting practices as it helps to maintain transparency	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
16. When FVA is implemented as per IFRS 9, it enables appropriate recognition of profit/loss of an asset	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
17. The stock market value and fair value measured information are correlated in Saudi Arabia	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION TO MAKE THIS SURVEY A SUCCESS